

Tools for the Evaluation and Impact Assessment of Co-Innovation

Version 1.0

Guide

How well are you working in partnership for innovation?

Are you a farmer, forester or other rural business? Are you interested in working with others to solve a tricky problem on your farm or develop a new product for your rural business? Have you discovered the many opportunities to apply for funding for an innovation project or other initiative? Are you already working in a partnership to find innovative solutions to your day-to-day challenges or missed opportunities? If you answered yes to all of these questions – please continue reading!

More and more people like you are coming together to combine their skills and knowledge in the so-called process of “co-innovation” (or interactive innovation). This process has many successes and some failures, and innovators like you are therefore asking questions ...

How effective is the co-innovation process in our group? Do we cooperate as smoothly as we planned in the beginning? What factors are hindering cooperation between members of our group? How do we report to our funder about progress with the project and its likely impact?

WHAT IS THIS GUIDE FOR?

This Guide introduces a range of methods and tools that can be used for the evaluation and impact assessment of any project or other initiative that involves groups working together for co-innovation.

It includes hands-on guidance for selecting one or more of 37 tools for assessing or evaluating the interactivity within a co-innovation project and/or the results and impact of the envisaged innovation. The tools have been tested in practice together with several groups in real-life settings and are now practice-ready.

All tools are available as stand-alone documents for download and individual use. They are each explained in an easy-to-read, step-by-step format together with tips and tricks for using them. This format aims to support users engaged in various types of innovation projects, agri-food or forestry initiatives, or broad industry networks. The tools are available in English only.

The key terms associated with the tools are explained later in this Guide. Other terms are defined in the *LIAISON Glossary*.

WHO IS THIS GUIDE FOR?

This Guide is suitable for anyone who wishes to evaluate, monitor, and improve an on-going co-innovation process, whether a formal project or more informal collaboration.

This encompasses a broad variety of potential users, including the coordinators of large-scale multi-actor projects, innovation support services facilitating the set-up and running of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups, or any other actors engaged with the broad range of co-innovation activities that exist in agriculture and forestry and their associated value chains. Users of the Guide might also work in other areas of rural development, including community-led local development (e.g. LEADER Local Action Groups).

In addition, the Guide aims to support the qualitative or quantitative assessment of the impact emerging from a technical, organisational or social solution delivered by a co-innovation (interactive innovation) project or similar initiative.

In simple terms, quantitative approaches can measure – in numbers – how well a project or an initiative is operating and how impactful it is. Qualitative methods can understand what is happening in interactive innovation processes and can inform project leaders and team members about how these processes can be enhanced.

HOW TO USE THIS GUIDE

There are 37 ready-to-use evaluation and impact assessment tools available via this Guide (see list below). Each tool has a name and a number and is quickly accessed by clicking on a link. The tools are stored on a publicly funded open access archive system called [Zenodo](#). All tools may be viewed online or downloaded.

Each tool includes four main elements:

MAA Scenario	 ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING
When to Implement	Crucial at team-building stage and used to assess and improve network members.
Group Size	Small to large multi actor group.
Level of Technical Difficulty	No technical skills required.

LIAISON Tool #1: Participatory Social Network Mapping & Appraisal	
PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC	
Purpose	Background
This tool is used to:	Consensus is...
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the types of actors involved in multi-actor teams, and the actors who may not but who ought to be involved. Sensitise and attune participants to the actor categories they are representing in multi-actor teams. Assess strengths and weaknesses of cooperative relationships within multi-actor teams. 	work, the air perspectives important, the formation, to each actor to identity, and etc. that the of multi-act

1. A list of seven ‘key identifiers’ (see Figure 1) indicates the tool’s suitability for the specific contexts in which they might be needed and used by a co-innovation partnership. This includes the prevailing Multi-actor Scenario (see Figure 2 and text below), when to implement the tool, group size, level of technical difficulty, the time needed, resources required, and potential for clustering with other tools;

2. An explanation of the purpose, background and logic of the tool with relevant information to help select the most appropriate tools for particular forms of co-innovation activities or the type of assessment challenges encountered.

LIAISON Tool #1: Participatory Social Network Mapping & Appraisal
Step 2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In a small group (up to 12) ask participants to cluster the sticky notes according to group identifiers. In a larger group, identify a representative from each actor category and invite them to approach the board and cluster the sticky notes according to actor categories. In the example to the right, participants have grouped the sticky notes into two categories: farmers and extension. Ask participants to draw a circle around the clustered post-its and to assign them an actor category label. In the example to the right, two labels are created: farmers and extension. Now we can see a graphical representation of the actor categories represented in the group, who is in

3. Guidance on how to implement the tool;

4. The results that can be expected from applying the tool.

ICON	KEY IDENTIFIERS
	<p>MAA Scenario What multi-actor scenario(s) does your assessment challenge relate to?</p>
	<p>When to implement? What exactly do you want this tool for? For example,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To build a co-innovation partnership? • To develop a new idea? • To prepare a decision? • to assess the impact of a particular activity?
	<p>Group size What size will be the group? A small group or a large consortium?</p>
	<p>Level of technical difficulty What technical skills (if any) or experiences are required for the use of this tool?</p>
	<p>Time needed How long does it take to use this tool? Is it hours or days? Is it used once-off or periodically?</p>
	<p>Resources required What resources are required? What materials is needed? Is particular equipment or expertise required? Is the use of the tool expensive?</p>
	<p>Clustering with other tools What other tools can this tool be paired with to provide a more comprehensive approach? Will this combination provide an added value for the assessment?</p>

Figure 1: List of 'key identifiers' to support the selection of tools according to the specific context and need (icons and translated text provided at the end of this document)

Selecting the ‘multi-actor’ scenario relevant to your evaluation/impact assessment

Partnerships for innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural development are often very diverse (the ‘multi-actor approach’). An effective working relationship between the partners is crucial for the success of the co-innovation (interactive innovation) process and the delivery of unique results and benefits (innovative solutions).

Implementation of the multi-actor approach typically involves specific scenarios that are characteristic of the various stages of the co-innovation process. These range from engaging and encouraging external actors or stakeholders to become involved through the process of co-creating new ideas and knowledge, to applying these innovative solutions in practice and assessing their impact. For the purposes of this Guide, a total of six scenarios are described in *Figure 2: Engaging and Incentivising, Interrogating, Creating, Addressing, Applying and Evaluation*.

ICON OF MAA SCENARIO	DESCRIPTION OF MAA SCENARIOS 1-6
<p>Engaging & Incentivising</p>	Engaging potential partners or stakeholders in an innovation group.
<p>Interrogating</p>	Interrogating existing knowledge from experts, literature, internet, social media etc.
<p>Creating</p>	Creating innovative solutions or products; participating in co-design processes; sharing knowledge and information
<p>Addressing</p>	Addressing particular challenges for the co-innovation project; solving technical or organisational problems
<p>Applying</p>	Applying knowledge and innovative solutions to other systems or particular contexts
<p>Evaluation & Impact Assessment</p>	Evaluation of innovation projects, their results and expected impacts; self-assessment of co-innovation partnerships.

Figure 2: Six ‘multi-actor scenarios’ relevant for evaluation/impact assessment

INDEX OF LIAISON TOOLS FOR EVALUATION AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT

Tools Inspired by Development Evaluation (DE) and Social Impact Management Planning (SIMP)

- Participatory Social Network Mapping & Appraisal
- Actor/Role Identification (ID)
- Personas: Understanding Our Stakeholders
- Ground Rules: Identification of Opportunities and Challenges of Agreement-based Cooperation
- Needs Register: Recording Stakeholders Needs & Assessing Responsiveness
- Motivations Register
- 'Hot Topics': Coalescing Interests Across Boundaries
- Goal Setting: Building Empathy One-to-One
- What, Who, Why, Where, When & How?
- Diagnostic Checklist as a Learning Tool for Developmental Evaluation (DE)
- 'Causes and Effects': Building Hypotheses: Linking Actions to Results
- Actions: Identification, Proof, Phase
- Mind Meitheal (Mind Community)
- Journey Mapping
- Impact Stories
- Appraisal of Group Dynamics
- Guide to The Leading/Bleeding Edge: Innovation Case Transfer
- Practicing Evaluative Thinking
- Evaluator Self-Assessment: Unconscious Bias
- Gender Appraisal
- Empowerment Appraisal
- System ID
- TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem-Solving)
- Unintended Impacts Mitigation

Tools inspired by SNA

- Social Network Analysis
- Interest-Influence Matrix
- Rainbow Diagram

Tools inspired by SNA, PIPA and PSC

- Diagnostic Checklist For Interactions
- Actors Monitoring Dashboard
- Stakeholder-Associated Risk Analysis
- Satisfaction Survey
- Monitoring Tool for Impacts

Classical tools

- Altmetrics
- Economic Performance Evaluation
- Indicator Dashboards
- Scientometrics, Patents and Spin-Offs

EXPLANATION OF KEY TERMS USED IN THIS GUIDE

Co-design is an on-going process of co-creating or co-adapting tools with users. Co-design is based on a distinct set of principles and practices for understanding problems and generating solutions. It signifies the active involvement of a diverse range of participants in exploring, developing, and testing responses to shared challenges.

Developmental Evaluation (DE) is a living, reflexive approach to evaluation and impact assessment. It evolves in response to project dynamics in 'real-time'. DE can be described as a multi-actor laboratory that not only charts, incrementally, how and why different types of impacts occur throughout the interactive innovation process. It generates and tests strategies to alter the course of innovation processes to enhance impacts but always in the eyes of the actors involved.

Evaluation is an evidence-based judgement of the extent to which an existing intervention is useful, effective, efficient, relevant to the current needs, coherent and whether it has achieved added value. Evaluation can have a variety of objectives, including to measure outcomes; to understand causal pathways generating changes; and to stimulate learning processes. There are several types of evaluation such as ex-ante evaluation (performed before the implementation of an intervention), mid-term evaluation (performed towards the middle of the implementation period) and ex-post evaluation (performed directly after the completion of an intervention). Impact evaluation is typically performed after an intervention has happened to assess its long-term outcomes, sustainability and unforeseen effects.

Impact assessment is part of the evaluation practices explained above. It is a form of outcome evaluation that assesses the net effect of a programme. The methodological approach is usually based on comparing outcomes and an estimate of what would have happened without the support programme. Impact assessment differs from impact evaluation, which takes place several years after an intervention has happened. It assesses the long-term outcome and the intervention's sustainability and unforeseen effects. Since impact assessment addresses outcomes, it can or should be done at any time of the process, including as a monitoring activity. In this document, it is always included when the general term 'Evaluation' is used.

Interactive innovation is an approach that has been introduced by the European Commission. It describes the collaboration between actors to make the best use of complementary types of knowledge (scientific, practical, organisational, etc.) in view of co-creation and diffusion of innovative solutions or opportunities, which are ready to implement in practice. Synonyms are 'co-creation', 'collaboration for innovation' or 'co-innovation'. Interactive innovation emerges from the context of the European Innovation Partnership 'Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (*EIP-AGRI*) and the so-called 'multi-actor approach'.

Methods are a collection of tools and processes that are useful together for a common aim.

Methodology is the logic that stands behind the selection of one or the other tool to construct a method.

Monitoring refers to on-going evaluation activities carried out by project and project managers who use a systematic collection of data on specified indicators. The aim is to provide the coordinators, project members and the main stakeholders of an on-going development intervention with indications that show the extent of progress and achievement of objectives and progress in the use of allocated funds. Continual data collection and self-reflection are intended to assist decision making throughout the co-creation process to improve them and achieve better impacts.

Users (or end-users) are individuals who ultimately use or are intended to use a product or service.

PIPA – Participatory Impact Pathway Assessment is a participatory approach allowing actors and change to mobilise and increase interactions within the innovation network.

Project or initiative is any form of entity or multi-actor group engaged in co-creation (interactive innovation), whether funded or non-funded, working for a defined period (project) or operating formally or informally.

PSC - Positive Social Change is an analytical framework that describes the processes intended to transform individuals, organisations, and institutions' thoughts and actions to improve societal well-being.

SNA - Social Network Analysis focuses on the investigation of patterns of relations and social interactions among individuals and organisations. SNA can be used to draw the network and calculate indicators reflecting the type and structure of the network at a time while identifying the interactivity level of relationships between stakeholders, the identification of the most powerful stakeholders, etc.

Self-evaluation is the internal and on-going evaluation activities carried out by projects; project managers and participants. These activities constitute the monitoring system of the project and are usually assisted by tools for data collection and reflection to help decision-making.

SIMP – Social Impact Management Planning is a management tool for addressing the social impacts of large-scale projects in an area or sector.

Tools are specific instruments that the LIAISON project recommends for use in the field to support evaluation and impact assessment or similar innovation group processes that require facilitation. All LIAISON tools are stand-alone PDF documents available for download and individual use.

Quantitative or 'classical' evaluation is focused on assigning numerical values (metrics) to the observed changes (outputs, outcomes, impacts) resulting from the interventions. Systematically, it intends to provide answers to questions such as: „How many?“, „How much?“, „How long?“ etc. Data collected from existing studies is enriched by field surveys, questionnaires, workshops, clinical trials etc. provides the foundation for quantitative analyses. As various innovative technologies became available (e.g. GIS, mobile phones, social media) they are also increasingly used for data collection. Quantitative evaluation relies on the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and other standards for statistics. Donors and evaluators are interested in gaining a bigger picture supported by numbers. Such data allows informed decision-making. Various principles and sophisticated approaches have evolved to standardise evaluation procedures and align them with the requirements of exact sciences such as randomised controlled trials and multivariate analyses.

Qualitative methods and tools enable a relatively straightforward observation and reporting about the changes when dealing with many beneficiaries and policy instruments. **Quantitative evaluation** is the widely preferred approach for tracking the performance of the implemented initiatives such as those financed by European Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation or European Agricultural Policy Programmes. It can also focus on assessing the interactivity of an innovation group.

DEVELOPMENT OF THIS GUIDE

This Guide and the associated tools were developed involving users from the agricultural and forestry industries and advisors, researchers, and representatives of governmental and non-governmental organisations. Actors from co-innovation projects and external stakeholders – both involved in ‘real life’ interactive innovation projects – used, adapted, configured and tested the tools in a ‘co-design’ process.

The index of tools consists of four sections. The tools in each section were co-designed with external participants by a *LIAISON partner* team:

- TEAGASC led the co-design of the tools inspired by Development Evaluation (DE) and Social Impact Management Planning (SIMP)
- FIBL team elaborated tools inspired by the Social Network Assessment (SNA)
- Madrid University (UPM) has co-ordinated the development of tools based on the SNA
- ‘Group de Brugge’ tested and further developed the so-called ‘classical’ tools for evaluation and impact assessment

ABOUT THE LIAISON PROJECT

The *LIAISON project* was funded by the research and innovation programme of the European Union. It brought together a broad range of individuals and organisations from across Europe with experience and understanding (both theoretical and practical) of co-innovation in agriculture, forestry and related rural activities. LIAISON aimed to produce easy-to-read guidance and other materials to support those participating in co-innovation projects and other similar initiatives.

In addition to this Guide, there are:

Five LIAISON How-to-Guides for innovation partnerships and networks that focus on:

- *'Coming Together'* as a group connecting individuals and organisations with complementary skills, knowledge and resources
- *'Good Planning'* of co-innovation projects, their structure and work plan
- *'Healthy Partnerships'* using tips and tricks for working in a multi-actor-project with shared rules and responsibilities
- *'Connected Partnerships'* ensuring the embeddedness of co-innovation groups in a wide network of stakeholders with additional expertise and an interest in the project's output
- *'Achieving Impact'* complementing this Guide for Evaluation and Impact Assessment with tips and tricks for groups, including good practice examples from the LIAISON team

LIAISON's *Guide for the Facilitation of Co-innovation Projects* provides access to several methods and tools that help to facilitate the following specific processes:

- the formation of co-innovation partnerships,
- co-design for the development and testing of innovative solutions, services or products
- dissemination and exploitation of the results of co-innovation projects.

About this LIAISON 'Handbook'

LIAISON (Better Rural Innovation: Linking Actors, Instruments and Policies through Networks) is a multi-actor project which has been funded within the EIP-Agri, an initiative launched by the European Commission in 2012 with its goal of fostering competitive and sustainable agriculture and forestry that “achieves more and better from less”.

This Guide for impact assessment with its 37 associated tools highlights the results of LIAISON's literature review about data collection and co-design activities. The aim is to help all, who use these tools, enhance the way they co-innovate in farming, forestry and rural development.

This short Guide for Evaluation and Impact Assessment of Co-Innovation Projects has been produced from a larger document written by Áine Macken-Walsh, Anna Maria Augustyn, Maddalena Bettoni, José María Díaz Puente, Aoife Forde, Robert Home, Martin Javornicky, Anita Naughton, Sylvain Quiédeville, and Dana Cristina Repede.

The editorial team responsible for the content of this Guide were Susanne von Münchhausen, Elena Claudia Ion and Mark Redman. Design work was by WERNERWERKE.

Thanks are also due to the partners in the LIAISON project that tested the tools with external project groups.

The information in this Guide is for general informational purposes only. Readers are advised to check any information against regulations or ways of working in their own locale. Any use of this information is at your own risk.

The LIAISON project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 773418. The responsibility for the information and views set out in this document lies entirely with the authors.

